

Intercrops and soil health in mountainous farms and rangelands

Intercropping is an ancestral technique, which consists of growing different types of grains and legumes (or other mixed crops) at the same time. This practice is beneficial in mountainous areas, as issues such as: depletion of soil nutrients, increased soil erosion, reduced soil biodiversity, condensation and reduced water infiltration, reduced system resilience prevail.

ESTABLISHMENT AND BENEFITS

Various combinations of crops can be used in the establishment according to the needs and availability of the soil, from the following: vegetables (cabbage, parsley, carrots, beans, potatoes, corn, tomatoes, peppers, zucchini), trees (walnuts, apples, hazelnuts, quinces, cherries, chestnuts), native plants (oregano).

Care must be taken for trees not intercepting the sun light for the vegetables and do not compete with them for nutrients. Intercropping with cereals, legumes and other compatible crops significantly enhances plant growth, reproductive characteristics, yield and fruit quality, while increasing soil health. The higher biomass production of intercropping and therefore the soil organic matter inputs increase increases soil health. It provides continuous improvements in key parameters such as soil organic carbon and microbial biomass. In addition, diversified intercropping enhances water use efficiency, moderates the soil microclimate and protects crops from climate variability.

Figure 1 Area of Potamia Karpenisi by Vlachos M.

Figure 2 Intercropping of potatoes and fruit trees on an agroforestry estate in the valley (Spring 2025) by Lappa V.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Overall, intercropping presents an ecologically sustainable pathway for the revitalization of fruit-based cropping systems, also known as permanent crops. By improving soil functionality, optimizing resource use and enhancing crop resilience, intercropping offers a transformative approach to achieving increased productivity while ensuring environmental stewardship in changing climate scenarios.

KEYWORDS

soil health, mountainous farms, rangelands, agroforestry, vegetables, trees, co-cultivation

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